

Deliverable 7.2: DEDALUS Communication Kit

D7.2: DEDALUS Communication Kit
WP 7, T7.2

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List of Acronyms

EC	European Commission
WP	Work Package
CMS	Content Management System
DoA	Description of the Action
WP	Work Package
CMS	Content Management System

0. Executive summary

The present deliverable aims to describe the main gateways of information and communication of the DEDALUS project: respectively, the project website, the leaflets and roll-up poster, the project presentation video and the social media.

In this deliverable, each communication material is deeply described from the initial stage of its design in terms of structure and layout, to the collection and creation of content and – when applicable (in case of the project website and presentation video) - to the technical implementation and monitoring.

The main communication and dissemination **targets** to whom these communication materials aim to speak are first the stakeholders of the project, who will be able to find in each material more general information about the project as well as updates on technical implementations.

The stakeholders of the project will also find on the website an important gateway of information and activities for their engagement, especially for those closely connected to the pilots.

The target audience of the project video, instead, is **quite wide**, ranging from the stakeholders that are connected to specific pilots both technical and non-technical, to similar initiatives, e.g. fellow projects, to possible replication-oriented stakeholders, and finally to what we can call general public.

Finally, since the beginning of the project, the social media presence (X/Twitter; LinkedIn and YouTube) is aimed at improving and enlarging the communication outreach of the project. The possibility of reaching targets that are not usually in touch with the ecosystem of European-funded projects is indeed one of the main reasons why the DEDALUS project endeavors to establish a social media presence.

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose and audience of the document

The scope of this report is to describe in detail the design and the content of the three main important communication materials developed within the DEDALUS Project: website, leaflet and roll-up poster, and presentation video.

The present deliverable aims at **describing the design and creation of the project's website**, from the initial stages of structure and layout design to the collection and creation of contents, including the technical implementation.

In addition to giving indications as to **how the website will aid the project's general communication and dissemination strategy overall**, this deliverable will also define **the strategy for future content updates** by specifying objectives in terms of update frequency and the partners' responsibility in the creation of website material.

The DEDALUS website can be found at the following address: <https://dedalus-horizon.eu/>.

The current deliverable also presents the steps the project went through to devise, design, produce, and distribute its **video**.

The video aims to present the manifold aspects of DEDALUS, the objectives, targets, and impacts the project will attain by implementing innovative technical solutions, such as the demand response, that will be integrated in the project pilots and other ones.

It has been produced in complete accordance with the visual identity of the project, by respecting its colours, purpose, and tone. It will be distributed mainly through the project website, DEDALUS social media channels and YouTube accounts.

The short presentation video has been developed and is being distributed by ICONS. It will be made available to the whole consortium to present DEDALUS at events, fairs, workshops, and training sessions.

This document also presents the **leaflet** developed for DEDALUS. The main goal of the flyer is to offer an overview of the project's approach, objectives, and impacts. It also features each partner's logo and their main contact details. Said flyer will be distributed at relevant events, such as conferences, workshops, and meetings, to support the dissemination activities. It will be translated into the local languages of DEDALUS pilots to better support local communication activities.

This document, finally, has a chapter dedicated to the project's **social media presence** developed since the beginning of the project and aimed at enlarging the target audience over the edges of the EU-funded projects' ecosystem.

1.2. Relation to other activities

Over the course of the project, the communication materials analysed in depth in this paper will play an important supporting role in disseminating project results and progress.

In particular, Leaflets-localized in content and language for greater understanding of the objectives pursued by DEDALUS will play an important role in the process of engaging local stakeholders where there is a presence of project pilots.

1.3. Structure of the document

This document is structured as follows:

- Chapter 1 is dedicated to a general overview of the main project's communication gateways and their specific objectives in terms of dissemination.
- Chapter 2 is dedicated to the project website, the main communication gateway of the project. In this chapter, it is deeply described the overall process of ideation, production and implementation of the website.
- Chapter 3 is focused on the analysis of the production and distribution of the project's leaflet and roll-up poster.
- Chapter 4 describes the entire process of design and production of the project's presentation video, since the development of the concept to its dissemination strategy.
- Chapter 5 offers an overview on the DEDALUS social media presence, to improve and enlarge the project's target audience over the edges of the EU-funded projects' ecosystem.

2. Project website

The project website design was firstly approached by ICONS team during the design of the **project landing page**, which was implemented in August 2023 (M4). At that point, though much of the structure of the contents for the complete website was still to be decided, the main graphic elements were set in place and have afterward been considered when designing the final website graphic appearance.

From the definition of the DEDALUS visual identity and the graphic elements used in the landing page, a more complex set of graphic elements was then developed for the main project website. In the following sections, the structure of the website contents and the design of its graphic appearance are shown, together with the process used by ICONS to produce them.

2.1. Website structure

As mentioned in the D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan, the design of the **contents structure** of the project website was undertaken at the beginning of M3 and has been subsequently defined. The contents have been provided both by the ICONS team, who prepared them to start from the DoA materials, and from consultations with Engineering, as project coordinator, and by the consortium partners that provided info regarding their own companies and the pilots.

The table below shows the website structure, divided into 7 sections.

Table 1: DEDALUS website structure

Section	Description
HOME PAGE	The official entry point of the website. It features a brief introduction and links to the most relevant sections. Starting from December 2023 (M8), the page embeds the project presentation video to quickly provide the user with the key elements of DEDALUS.
ABOUT	This section includes the main objectives, the expected results, the presentation of the consortium. For each project partner there is a link to the company website.
PILOTS	The section presents the seven DEDALUS pilots. For each one, its main characteristics and the specific solutions being implemented are featured.
NEWS	The section will contain the news published by the project, such as press releases, journalistic articles and interviews, page flows, newsletters, videos, internal publications like podcasts, info-sheets and Best Practice books.

EVENTS	This section lists both events organised by the project and others such as those organised by sister projects to support their Communication & Dissemination (C&D) campaigns and allow the whole projects' cluster to achieve larger impacts.
RESOURCES	This page acts as a repository for official documents and allows users to download public materials produced by the project, such as deliverables, reports, publications and so on.
COMMUNICATION	This page acts as a repository for all the documents about the communication activities and the graphic materials (leaflets; roll-up poster, brandbook, for example).
CONTACTS	Contact details of the project Communication secretariat.

The structure of the website was carefully planned and designed with a specific attention to the **user experience**, in order to facilitate the exploration of different sections and pages for the users. These paths have been designed to make the more technical information about the project's technologies easy to find for those users that are interested in them, without crowding the navigation in general, leaving the less professional audiences free to explore the more understandable and easy sections of the website.

The **News and Events section** is given special prominence on the homepage, as the content that will most frequently be updated. Seeing new and different content on the homepage as they return, will encourage visitors to visit the website continuously over the months of the project, this way being more likely to get to know about project updates as soon as they are published. A part the content is directly published on the website, a link to the social channels (LinkedIn; X; YouTube) has also been provided.

2.2. Layout

The layout design for the DEDALUS website was planned, as mentioned before, starting from the visual identity developed at the beginning of the project and keeping in mind the materials already developed for the landing page.

Figure 1: DEDALUS Homepage

Pilots

Over the course of the project, the Dedalus framework will be applied, implemented, and validated in **7 real-life pilots across 7 countries**.

The large geographical coverage of the pilot sites aims to support the large-scale EU wide replicability and market take-up of solutions in different socio-economical contexts to maximize the impact of Dedalus services across Europe.

1 Austria

FRONT RUNNER • VIENNA

This pilot is led by OurPower, a cooperative based in Vienna, operating a P2P marketplace for matching RES electricity generated by its members with consumers. This pilot, composed by **84 private rentable serviced apartments and 20 commercial premises**, is equipped with 226 kWp rooftop and balcony PV system, 200 kWh battery storage, slow and fast EV charging stations, and baseline BEMS. On an annual average, **around 30% surplus electricity** is generated and traded on the OurPower platform. Nearly 800 customers, including 620 households, 113 farmers, and 48 SMEs, with an annual consumption of 4.6 GWh/a, buy electricity from the marketplace.

SCOPE

To utilize a building-level Demand Response program, coordinating energy assets in the building to smooth the statistical load profile and offer excess flexibility in a demand response scheme.

SOLUTIONS

Customer cockpit with nudging app for customer engagement.

TECHNOLOGICAL INNOVATION

Flexibility pre-aggregation for building-level energy community

Figure 2: DEDALUS - Pilots' section

2.3. Website Implementation

After the design phase was completed, the collection and creation of content began, which involved both the team in ICONS and the consortium. The website was meanwhile created in a test environment by the developers and later populated with the contents. An optimization phase followed, during which the technical components were tested, and the contents were validated by ENG as project coordinator.

Finally, the website was transferred from the testing environment and put **live on the domain** thus substituting the landing page, by the end of M6 (October 2023) as per Description of the Action (DoA).

2.3.1. Content collection and creation

The contents of the initial release of the DEDALUS website are mainly institutional and **aim at presenting the project and its objectives for the months to come**. They have been therefore taken mainly from the DoA and the technical sections of the Grant Agreement (GA).

The texts have anyways been simplified and re-written using easier-to-understand lexicon, avoiding acronyms as much as possible and focusing the most relevant aspects in terms of communication.

The consortium was involved in the preparation of content for the collection of information for the partners' pages and for the **pilots' descriptions**.

2.3.2. Interactive features

Although the website will act mainly as an information gateway in the first months after its online, there are several features that enable the users to interact with it and to engage with its contents. The main feature available for users that are particularly interested in the project's advancement and would like to receive constant updates is the registration to the newsletter. Through a form accessible from all website pages, users can submit their e-mail address. The collection of contacts that will happen through this form will constitute in time a **database of contacts** owned by the project that can be outreached to invite them to future events, engagement activities and newsletter subscription.

Figure 3: Newsletter registration button

The “Resources” section is also dedicated to the interaction with users, since there they’ll be able to **find and download all the public documents produced by the project**, such as deliverables, publications, scientific papers, and other materials. Documents can be filtered by type and language and will be freely available for download.

Figure 4: A screenshot of "Resources" section

2.3.1. Technical implementation

As it was done for the project's landing page, the website has been implemented using **WordPress content management system (CMS)**, an open-source solution enabling easy and smooth management of content also after the project completion. All the specific features of the website use WordPress plugins to function and are managed by the ICONS team about the contents and by an ICONS developer about the implementation.

A WordPress plugin is also used to manage the Newsletter of the project, in terms of collection of contacts, composition of the newsletter and mailing engine.

The website is hosted on Register.it, a renowned Italian provider for both domain purchase and hosting. The server farms of Register.it are located within Europe, ensuring that European regulations apply regarding data protection and privacy.

2.3.2. Acknowledgments, legal notices, and personal data management

To be compliant with the Grant Agreement obligations, the website displays in all pages a **footer that acknowledges the funding received**, along with the emblem of the European Union.

Since DEDALUS also collects data from the users that subscribe to the newsletter service, the website also displays a **Privacy Policy** that informs the users of their rights and explains how their data are managed and processed within ICONS. The users' data are stored on the server where the whole website is hosted and are protected by appropriate security measures.

Alongside the Privacy Policy, a **Cookies Policy** is also available for consultation, in which the cookies used by the website are listed. Cookies can be accepted or refused by the visitors when they access the website through a pop-up banner that is displayed at the bottom of the webpage.

Privacy notice

Introduction

Dear Subscriber,

We are glad to share with you the latest news on the developments of the Dedalus Horizon project, as well as on future developments of this research area. This Privacy Notice is a document addressing you as Data Subject, i.e. the owner of your personal data. It explains which personal data we collect and how we use it.

Figure 5: A framework of the DEDALUS website privacy notice

5. Cookies Policy

5.1 WordPress Session Cookies

Cookies are small text files that are stored on the User's computer's browser directory when visiting certain websites. The website uses cookies for specific and limited purposes, namely to provide easier navigation and for the purposes of internal security, of statistical analysis related to navigation and of system administration.

Session cookies allow Users to be recognized within a website so any page changes or item or data selection you do is remembered from page to page. Session cookies are temporarily stored in the computer memory only during a User's browsing session and are automatically deleted from the User's computer when the browser is closed. Persistent cookies remain in the browser's subfolder and are activated again once the User visits the website that created that particular cookie thus facilitating the navigation and making it faster (with the "keep me logged in" option). Analytical cookies collect anonymous data for internal purposes with the aim of providing a better browsing experience to the User.

Figure 6: A framework of the DEDALUS website cookie policy

2.4. Website maintenance and dissemination

In the following months of project activity, it is foreseen that **the website contents will be updated regularly and on special occasions**, such as the achievement of project milestones or significant advancement in the technical works implementation.

2.4.1. Content curation

The updates on regular basis will mainly regard the **News and Events sections**, through the publication of updates on the project works or participation of partners at events. While ICONS will take care of the publication of said news, the provision of content will be the responsibility of the partners, who will be in charge of reporting to ICONS all the relevant activities, along with the necessary information and pictures or video materials.

Another kind of update that will happen regularly will be the **publication of journalistic news**, produced by the ICONS journalists' team, **and of press releases** about the project's advancements. The press releases will be prepared either by ICONS or by other partners, depending on the nature of the content promoted.

Finally, about the more sporadic updates, they will mainly concern the **publication of documents and materials** in the Resources section, or **the update of the contents in the Project or Pilots sections**, to be carried out after particularly big developments or at the achievements of project milestones.

2.4.2. The website as a communication and dissemination platform

Through a number of initiatives, **the website will act as a platform or gateway for the communication and dissemination materials**, since it will make available for all stakeholders the materials that will be developed by the project. For example, the project presentation video produced in December 2023 (M8) is available on the website, as well as any material or news related to the stakeholders' engagement.

Moreover, towards the end of the project, **materials specifically related to dissemination** - such as info-packs, best practices and possibly the outcomes of workshops and webinars - will be made available for download or consultation.

Although the project will in general employ many other channels for communication and dissemination (see D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan), the website will act as a repository of all materials - Resources section - and as a chronicle of the different activities

carried out – News and Events sections – that will give the visitors a clear idea of the whole project’s activity and engagement with its stakeholders.

2.4.3. Monitoring

The performances of the website and its activity will be **monitored automatically through MATOMO¹**, a free and open-source tool to monitor the website traffic client both client and server sides. This will give insights into the number of visitors, their activity on the website, the path they followed to arrive on the website and the kind of navigation they had through the different sections.

Data thus gathered will be used as a KPI to assess the performance of the website and will be presented to the whole consortium at project meetings and in deliverables and will be the basis for any corrective action that will be deemed necessary during the project duration.

The ICONS team will evaluate together with the coordinator and the consortium the necessity and opportunity for major modifications to the website structure and functionalities, keeping in mind the needs of partners and activities, the users’ experience on the website and the availability of resources within ICONS budget.

For a deeper analysis of the ICONS monitoring activity, see D7.1 (Communication and Dissemination Plan).

¹ <https://matomo.org/free-software/>

content of the leaflets remains consistent, offering brief descriptions of the activities and solutions to be implemented, along with an introduction to the project framework.

3.1.2. Targets

The main targets of the leaflets are the **stakeholders connected to the pilots** and in particular the **local citizens and stakeholders**. These targets are expected to be well acquainted with the pilots but to have a limited technical background, especially about the specific solutions and works that DEDALUS is going to deploy.

For this reason, three main decisions were taken with regard to the concept and design of the leaflets:

1. The **format** was chosen to be compact and user-friendly with the aim of focusing readers' attention on a few key concepts while making the leaflet easy to carry and to pick up in different contexts.
2. The **tone of voice and the language used** was planned as quite simple and easy to understand, omitting the more technical information and focusing instead on the general objectives of the DEDALUS solutions.
3. The leaflets have been produced in **local languages**, Catalan, Italian, Greek, Danish and German, so that the local audience, they are aimed to, could more easily interact with the contents.

3.1.3. Graphic concept

The design of the leaflet was realized keeping in mind the above-mentioned considerations about objectives and targets. Opting for a compact format and prioritizing visuals over text was a decision taken in order to maximize impact and engagement.

In line with DEDALUS's graphic identity, the leaflet's design ensures consistency across the various communication channels of the project.

To convey information in a clear and engaging way, the leaflet's layout was structured with well-spaced boxes using the DEDALUS main colors to highlight the impacts of the project.

3.1.4. Text production and translation

The production of the texts for leaflets was performed initially by ICONS, taking as a starting point the texts previously produced for the website. A further help from partners was given about the translations into local languages. All texts were also validated by the project coordinator.

3.1.5. Expected distribution

The leaflets are designed to reach out to the stakeholders related to the pilots and their distribution will therefore be focused on local events that involve the tenants and stakeholders of the buildings. Another good occasion to create engagement and to spread the word about the project will be municipality initiatives in the relevant districts.

The specific means and channels for distribution will anyway be in the hands of the local partners related to the pilots, to identify the best ones to reach the targets, considering the local peculiarities and specificities of the involved neighbourhoods.

3.2. Roll up poster

DEDALUS roll-up poster is one of the main communication tools. Available only in English, it is designed to provide DEDALUS stakeholders with a concise and exhaustive overview of the project. It will be used by the partners during events, conferences, workshops. It will be available in two copies.

More specifically, the roll-up poster presents the following aspects:

- Description of the project and main objectives;
- A specific focus on the expected impacts foreseen by the project;
- The consortium (via the partners' logos);
- Contact details, social media channels and EU funding.

dedalus

Data-driven Residential Energy Carrier-agnostic Demand Response Tools and Multi-value Service

Dedalus is a 3-year project that aims at designing, developing, and demonstrating a demand-response ecosystem for residential buildings. This ecosystem optimizes and manages automated demand response and caters to all energy carriers.

Business level	Technological level	Social level
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 15% Increase in the energy-efficient of the pilot buildings, and cheaper energy bills for residential users at 10% 15% Cost reduction of the overall energy system >25% Reduction of demand response intervention costs after 5 years 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 12% Smart residential asset types ready for demand response after 3 years >7 New aggregation models and data-driven services >2 Digital tools to facilitate consumer activation and market participation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 45% Increased share of energy consumption data by active consumers after 5 years >18-20% Carbon emission reduction in the areas of the 7 pilots 15-20% Increased share of aggregated flexibility achieved by pilot users

During the project, the Dedalus framework is applied, implemented, and validated in 7 real-life pilots across Europe.

DISCOVER MORE: www.dedalus-horizon.eu

#DEDALUS-EUproject @DEDALUS-EU

Meet our Partners

For details the European Union views are expressed in the Financial Report of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or its member states. Neither the European Union nor the granting institution can be held responsible for them.

Figure 8: DEDALUS Rollup poster

4. Project presentation video

The production of the DEDALUS project video was foreseen for December 2023 (M8), to offer **the public and stakeholders** a quick way to **get to know the project**, in a moment when most of its activities are still in their early stages.

The video integrates the information available on the website by giving a quick overview of the project. The adopted terminology and tone of voice are clear and easy to understand. For a part of the public, it may work as the first introduction to DEDALUS that will later be complemented by richer and more in-depth information from the website and other communication and dissemination materials.

The video is 1:07 minutes long and accessible from the project's website and the DEDALUS YouTube channel.

Figure 9: A frame of DEDALUS presentation video

4.1. Objectives

As mentioned in the D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan, the project video aims at giving a **brief overview of the activities to be performed by DEDALUS**, with a **focus on conveying the concepts** that underlie the whole activities' structure and without being too specific and technical about the single solutions that are to be implemented.

From a communication point of view, the video is expected to work as a **first contact point between the viewers and the project**, or, in case they access it through the website, to be one of the first means they can use to get to know the project, before diving into the more extensive information there provided. In this regard, the video aims at making the viewers interested enough to want to know more about DEDALUS, therefore leading them either to the website or to other communication tools.

4.2. Targets

The target audience of the project video is **quite wide**, ranging from the stakeholders that are connected to specific pilots both technical and non-technical, to similar initiatives, e.g. fellow projects, to possible replication-oriented stakeholders and finally to what we can call general public.

For this reason, as mentioned before, **the tone of voice of the video is rather simple and understandable**, but the script and the visual contents were thought in order **not to trivialize the scope of the project** and retain the interest of more skilled and technically savvy stakeholders.

The future DEDALUS video production will be on the other hand more focused on specific targets and will therefore be more diversified, both in terms of contents and of language, presenting each time different aspects of the project and its results.

4.3. Concept

The DEDALUS video stands out for its ability to play on two distinct visual planes. On the one hand, it works on emotionality, through everyday situations it allows viewers to emotionally immerse themselves in family and social situations. On the other hand, through more landscape and abstract images it tells the context across the board, making it accessible to a wider audience. Graphic interventions emphasize key points, clarifying crucial elements that might not otherwise emerge clearly. In short, DEDALUS offers a complete visual experience, combining emotion, narrative, and graphic interventions.

The family and friendship metaphor also led the way to the use of examples and visualizations for the presentation of complex and difficult concept in a simplified way: this method was considered more compact and much more effective in terms of communicating the whole range of technical solutions used by DEDALUS, instead of an analytical approach, that could have given a very pedantic mood to the video.

Figure 10: Framework of Dedalus presentation video

The graphic implementation of the video was **based on the visual identity of the project** that was developed in June 2023 (M2) and is fully shown in D7.1 Communication and Dissemination Plan. Particular attention was put into the production of a medium that could be perceived as coherent as possible with the rest of the communication activities of the project.

Figure 11: A framework of the presentation video with the project's logo

4.4. Presentation video process

The production of the video followed different steps that can be summarised as follows:

1. Concept identification – The identification of the objectives, targets, and main contents of the video, followed by the design of the main creative idea.
2. Storyboard production – The main moments, or scenes, of the video were specified, as well as the delivery of all the contents and ideas the video aimed at communicating. The Storyboard was produced as a document that showed very roughly how the video would play out and the metaphors and visualisation that were to be used later.
3. Script writing – After the identification of the video's scenes, the precise script for the voice-over was written, choosing which data and which aspects of the contents were most apt to accompany the images. The script was approved by ENG as project's coordinator.
4. Shooting – The video was finally shot, putting into practice the decisions taken in the previous phases.
5. Speaker registration – The voiceover was registered in two different takes, to time the images in the best possible way.
6. Postproduction – Graphic interventions and slight visual corrections were added, along with the editing of the different scenes.
7. Subtitles addition – The video was finalised with English subtitles,

The whole process, from the concept definition to the finalisation of the video, took about four months of work, there including the valuable input and feedback provided by the coordinating team.

4.5. Dissemination

The next step after the project video production has been its distribution. The process was started during December 2023 (M8) after the release of the video but will continue in the following months, thanks to the joint efforts of the whole DEDALUS consortium.

The first step for the video distribution has been the **creation of a DEDALUS YouTube channel** that will host the project video and all the rest of the video production of the project. The availability of the videos on YouTube will ensure good exposure and the possibility to be easily found through search engines by users, besides making it easy to embed the video on other portals and most of all to track visualizations in a unified manner.

The video was then **linked to the project's website**, where it will be visible to all the visitors, as a mean of first introducing the project and its objectives. The video will also be further shared on **social media**, both by the project itself and by the project partners, and through the project's **newsletter**.

Further offline dissemination will be performed by the whole consortium in the occasion of **events and workshops**, where a synthetic and dynamic presentation of DEDALUS will be the starting point for discussion.

The results of the above-mentioned dissemination will be tracked and monitored by ICONS over the course of the project.

Figure 12: A frame of the presentation video

5. Social media

The social media presence of the DEDALUS project is aimed at **improving and enlarging the communication outreach of the project**. The possibility of reaching targets that are not usually in touch with the world of European-funded projects is indeed one of the main reasons why the DEDALUS project endeavors to establish a social media presence.

Figure 13: DEDALUS social media presence

5.1. Social media strategy

The DEDALUS **Social Media Strategy** is based on the following aspects:

- **Targets specification** – the targets DEDALUS wants to reach on social media and the most effective interaction models;
- **Channels identification** – the most appropriate social media to establish a presence on (based on the project’s stakeholders as identified in D6.1 (Preliminary Exploitation Plan) and D7.1 (Communication and Dissemination Plan) and their social media habits);
- **Frequency and timing** - the posting rate of each channel and reasoning to be considered when choosing a day or time for posting, if any;
- **Topics and content types** – the topics to be communicated, according to the selected targets and the specificity of each channel, as well as the types of contents to be thus shared, from the project itself or other sources;
- **Content creation and community management** – the expected contribution from ICONS and the other partners, both in the proposal and creation of appropriate contents and in the management of communities of users

The first version of the project social media strategy was finalized in June 2023 (M2). This foresaw the opening of the **Twitter** account DEDALUS_EU, which was launched in the same month. The account is animated on a weekly basis with different kinds of posts to both expand the DEDALUS community and boost its engagement.

A YouTube channel was opened in December 2023 to host the project video production (see Chapter 4).

A LinkedIn company page was opened in August 2023 (M4) to reach out to professionals and stakeholders in the Energy field.

To track online conversations about DEDALUS, the hashtag #DEDALUSEU was launched at the beginning of the project (June 2023). It is monitored by ICONS as part of the activity outlined in D7.1 (Communication and Dissemination Plan).

Over the next months, efforts will be focused on increasing the online community and its engagement with project content. In particular, DEDALUS products such as deliverables or scientific papers will be widely promoted.

Finally, social media campaigns will be considered in line with the media agenda and on the occasion of relevant transnational celebration days.

For a deep analysis of the social media presence and its monitoring, see D7.1.

- ²Twitter: https://twitter.com/DEDALUS_EU
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/dedalus-eu/>

- ² Twitter: https://twitter.com/DEDALUS_EU
- LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/dedalus-eu/>
- Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/@DEDALUS-EUproject>

DEDALUS EU
85 follower
1s • 🔒

🗨️ Let's delve deeper into **#DEDALUS_EU**: what's the project about?

Dedalus wants to combine leading-edge **#ICT** technologies with social and behavioral dimensions to ensure automated and **#blockchain**-based demand response across **#residential** buildings.

👉 Visit our website to learn more: <https://lnkd.in/dbgxbTiw>

what is DEDALUS?

Dedalus project aims to design, develop, and demonstrate SSH-Driven multi-value energy carrier-agnostic demand response ecosystem, tailored to optimize and manage automated demand response in residential buildings.

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Elena Gaboardi e 19 altre persone 4 diffusioni post

DEDALUS EU PROJECT @DEDALUS_EU · Dec 4, 2023

📷 We have just concluded the first day of our second plenary meeting, which is being hosted in Rome by our coordinator @EngineeringSpa!

The meeting goal was to assess together the first 6 months of **#DEDALUS_EU** and plan the future months. Stay tuned for more tomorrow!

National Technical University of Athens and 9 others

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Figure 14: Examples of social media posts

Conclusions

This deliverable presents the overall communication materials developed in the field of DEDALUS during the first eight months of this project.

Partners can refer to this communication kit for their dissemination activities in the field of the DEDALUS project.

Also, it is focused on a deep description of those materials that the partners involved in the activities in the pilots can use for their co-creation activities and engagement of local stakeholders.

The channels and materials illustrated in the current deliverable will ensure awareness, engagement, and uptake between professional stakeholders and the general public.

The current deliverable is a living document; so, it will be updated throughout the whole project to fine-tune the strategy and add new possible materials.